

Report – Dynamic PEMWE system model

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Abstract: *A dynamic PEMWE system model is developed to demonstrate technical feasibility and evaluate the performance of a wind-powered PEMWE system. Details of the models including electrochemical equations, energy and mass balances are described in the report.*

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1. Project Brief

The work performed in the report was done in conjunction with research activity in WP6 of Haeolus, an EU project. Hydrogen-Aeolic Energy with Optimised eLectrolysers Upstream of Substation (Haeolus). The Haeolus project aims to achieve several key objectives. Firstly, the project endeavours to address the issue of wind power saturation, i.e. that the value of wind power capacity significantly diminishes beyond 20% penetration in the energy system. This decline is attributed to factors such as the need for greater reserve capacity during low wind conditions, reduced efficiency of reserve plants operating below full capacity, and elevated transmission losses when exporting power from high wind potential areas, which typically have weaker grids. To enable higher wind-power penetration in the European grid, Haeolus will demonstrate innovative control strategies, mitigating the unpredictability of power produced by wind farms as elaborated in Figure 1. Secondly, the project focuses on demonstrating multiple use cases for hydrogen-wind systems, encompassing energy storage, mini-grid, and fuel production. Control strategies of such systems tailored to each operational mode will be developed and tested in laboratory and field settings, ensuring global relevance. Thirdly, Haeolus, with the unique capability of its electrolyser manufacturer, will demonstrate PEM technology on a large scale, providing a benchmark for comparison and exploring synergies between the two technologies (wind turbines and PEM water electrolyser). Additionally, the project aims to showcase the remote operation of a hydrogen-wind system, crucial for wind farms in remote or offshore locations.

This report details a PEMWE system model, which was developed to address the challenges posed by the dynamic integration of an intermittent electrical source with an electrolysis system.

Figure 1 PEM water electrolyser powered by wind farm schematic. The hydrogen produced is stored in H₂ storage (hydrogen tank), which is then utilised to generate electricity using a PEM fuel cell system.

2. Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) water electrolyser

A PEM water electrolyser (PEMWE) cell is an electrochemical device that uses electricity to split water into hydrogen and oxygen gases. It employs a solid polymer electrolyte membrane to facilitate the ion transport occurring within the cell. The PEM electrolysis cell consists of two electrodes, an anode, and a cathode, separated by a thin polymer membrane (commonly, a Nafion™ membrane). When an electric current is applied, water molecules at the anode undergo oxidation, releasing oxygen gas (O₂), positively charged hydrogen ions (protons, H⁺), and electrons.

The protons produced migrate through the PEM to the cathode side, while the negatively charged electrons travel through an external circuit to the cathode,

At the cathode, the protons and electrons combine, forming hydrogen gas (H₂). The membrane in PEM electrolysis is selective, allowing the passage of protons, while restricting the crossover of gases. This design prevents the mixing of hydrogen and oxygen gases, enhancing safety.

In the context of a PEMWE system, the balance of plant (BoP) encompasses three crucial subsystems: hydrogen management, water/thermal management, and the power conditioning unit. The hydrogen produced in the electrolysis process carries impurities, including traces of oxygen, water vapor, and other potential contaminants. To ensure the production of high-purity hydrogen suitable for diverse applications, purification methods such as pressure swing adsorption (PSA) or membrane separation are employed. These methods selectively eliminate impurities by leveraging differences in their adsorption or permeation properties, resulting in purified hydrogen gas, typically with a purity exceeding 99.9%¹. The purified hydrogen can undergo further compression if necessary for long-term storage.

The dimension and weight of an electrolyser system can vary among suppliers and system sizes. As an illustrative example, the 2.5 MW system (HyLYZER 500) from Cummins is delivered in a two-container system. The power supply is accommodated in a 40 ft container, weighing 23.3 tons, while the electrolyser system is housed in a 40 ft container, weighing 28 tons. These specifications provide insights into the physical characteristics of PEMWE systems, emphasizing the importance of considering such aspects in system deployment and integration.

¹ Grigoriev, S. A., et al. (2009). Hydrogen safety aspects related to high-pressure polymer electrolyte membrane water electrolysis. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy.

As mentioned in the earlier section one of the aims of the project is to demonstrate different uses of wind-powered hydrogen production, and one such use case is PEMWE as a grid service. This means that PEMWE must be capable of quickly adjusting to the varying wind power injection. The ramp rate of a PEM water electrolyser is the speed at which the electrical power input to the system can be adjusted. This parameter is a critical measure of the system's responsiveness to fluctuations in electrical load or power demand. Typically expressed as the rate of change of power input per unit of time, the PEM electrolyser stack's documented ramp rate falls within the range of 10-50% of rated capacity per second for increasing hydrogen production and up to 50% per second for decreasing hydrogen production^{2,3}. It is essential to recognize that the practical ramping rates are expected to be lower, primarily due to the response time of BoP components. For instance, in the Cummins HyLYZER series containerized PEM system, the reported ramp rate is specified as $\leq 20\%$ per second, which highlights the practical considerations and limitations associated with achieving high ramping rates, such as the inherent dynamics of the system's BoP components.

PEM electrolysers operate at relatively low temperatures (typically between 60 and 80 degrees Celsius), which reduces energy consumption and allows for faster start-up times. The solid polymer electrolyte membrane, Nafion™, provides high selectivity and permeability for proton transport and can withstand high current densities. PEM water electrolysis is a key technology in the production of hydrogen for various applications, including PEM fuel cell-powered heavy-duty transport, energy storage, and industrial processes. It enables the generation of clean hydrogen from renewable energy sources, contributing to the development of a sustainable and decarbonized energy system.

The current state-of-the-art (SoA) and future targets set by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU) defined by key performance indicators (KPIs) in hydrogen production from renewable electricity, particularly for energy storage and grid balancing, are crucial benchmarks. Some targets are contingent upon the profitability of the services rendered to the grid through the incorporation of flexibility and/or reactivity. The KPIs for PEMWE are shown in Table 1.

² Tjarks, G. et al. (2016). Dynamic Operation of Electrolyzers-Systems Design and Operating Strategies. In Hydrogen Science and Engineering : Materials, Processes, Systems and Technology

³ Mohanpurkar, M et al. (2017). Electrolyzers Enhancing Flexibility in Electric Grids. Energies

Table 1 Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for a PEMWE system ⁴.

No	Parameter	Unit	SoA	2024	2030
1	Electricity consumption @ nominal capacity	kWh/kg	55	52	48
2	Capital cost	€/(kg/d)	2100	1550	1000
2	Capital cost	€/kW	900	700	500
3	O&M cost	€/(kg/d)/y	41	30	21
4	Hot idle ramp time	sec	2	1	1
5	Cold start ramp time	sec	30	10	10
6	Degradation	%/1,000h	0.19	0.15	0.12
7	Current density	A/cm ²	2.2	2.4	3
8	Use of critical raw materials as catalysts	mg/W	2.5	1.25	0.25

⁴ Hydrogen Europe Research. 2020. Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda: Clean Hydrogen for Europe.

Figure 2: Simplified process flow diagram of PEMWE system. The highlighted part which is PEMWE and Feed/cooling subsystem with thermal management is the one under focus in this report. Downstream (Gas Liquid Separation) processing is excluded. Numbers mentioned in circles indicate the sequence of operation.

The process starts with the introduction of deionised (DI) water to the oxygen gas-liquid separator (V-102) using the pump (P-101). The hot water (>333 K) from V-102 is then pumped (P-102) and cooled (333 K) in the heat exchanger (E-101) before being introduced into the PEMWE stack (EL-101). On the anode side, saturated oxygen gas and liquid water exit the electrolyser. The bulk of the liquid water is separated from the anode stream using the gas-liquid separator (V-102), where separation happens due to gravity. On the cathode side, saturated hydrogen gas and liquid water exit the electrolyser. The hydrogen gas and liquid water are separated using a gas-liquid separator (V-101), where separation occurs due to gravity. The hydrogen from V-101 is saturated with water vapour, therefore, to remove the water, the binary mixture is cooled in the heat exchanger (E-102), and then the condensed water is separated from the stream using a demister (V-103). A similar process is used on the oxygen side. The water extracted from the demisters is sent back to their respective gas-liquid separators. Level control loops are set in place to manage the water level inside each of the gas-liquid separators, and the pressure is controlled on both the anode and cathode using pressure control valves.

3. PEM modelling

Proper operation and control of the RE-based electrolyser and hydrogen storage systems require accurate and comprehensive models of the system components especially the electrolyser. The interconnection of physical domains within an electrolyser establishes a dynamic relationship, where alterations in one domain significantly influence others. Consequently, physics-based water electrolyser models necessitate the introduction of coupled sub-models to accurately emulate this interdependency. These models employ electrochemical, thermal, and mass transport sub-models to comprehensively depict the operational dynamics of the electrolyser stack.

Electrochemical models provide a comprehensive depiction of the electrical potential necessary for the electrolysis reaction and the associated overpotential stemming from irreversible processes or nonequilibrium operating conditions. These models systematically quantify the voltage drop attributable to inefficiencies within the electrolytic cell, thereby elucidating the consequential impact on the operational characteristics of the cell.

Thermal models are designed to elucidate the complex interplay of heat transfer and temperature dynamics within the PEMWE system. These models extend their scope to incorporate irreversibilities contributing to heat generation, thereby introducing thermal dynamics that influence the overall performance of the system.

Additionally, mass transfer and reaction models serve as invaluable tools for simulating the intricate movement of water, oxygen, and hydrogen across the cell. These models encompass phenomena including but not limited to proton transfer across the membrane, and gas crossover, which governs mass transport within the PEMWE system.

3.1. Electrochemical models

The electric potential applied to the electrodes induces redox reactions that drive the operation of a water electrolyser. Thus, modelling of such potential helps in understanding its influence on the system efficiency and is important to design control systems⁵.

$$U_{cell} = U_{rev} + E_{act} + U_{ohm} + E_{con} + E_{bub}$$

1)

U stands for cell potential and E for electrode potential. The PEM water electrolyser cell potential (U_{cell}) is deconstructed into constituent elements representing distinct losses and irreversibilities within the electrolysis process, as elucidated in the equation above. The reversible potential (U_{rev}) serves as a fundamental component, representing the theoretically required voltage necessary to carry out the water electrolysis reaction based on thermodynamics. Ohmic overpotential (U_{ohm}) encapsulates the modelling of membrane resistance, representing a critical element in the overall voltage profile. Activation overpotential (E_{act}) characterises the loss for initiating the electrochemical reaction at the

⁵ Görgün, H. (2006). Dynamic modelling of a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.

electrodes, offering insights into the kinetics of the process. Concentration overpotential (E_{con}) plays a crucial role that accounts for potential losses attributed to mass transfer limitations and concentration gradients in both the anode and cathode regions. Furthermore, the bubble overpotential (E_{bub}) component models losses arising from the formation of bubbles on the electrodes and membrane surfaces, reducing the active area available for the reactions to occur. The bubble overpotential is assumed to be insignificant.

3.1.1. Equivalent circuit models

The simplest of PEMWE models are based on experimentally derived empirical parameters that allow the operation of a WE to be simplified into a well-studied concept⁶. In the context of a PEMWE, the system's operation is elucidated through the utilization of a static equivalent circuit⁷. The model shown in Figure 3 can be applied to varying sizes of PEM electrolysers including various combinations of cells placed in series and/or in parallel. The proposed equivalent electrical circuit model is simple to implement and provides the ability to analyse the electrical response and performance of the PEM electrolyser system, for various grid and off-grid applications, such as energy storage in the form of hydrogen.

The circuit shown in Figure 3 incorporates a resistor placed in series with a reversible voltage, giving a linear approximation of the current-voltage ($I-V$) characteristic curve. Within this framework, the critical voltage for the initiation of current flow is denoted as U_{int} , while the slope of the curve is characterized by the resistor, R_i . This resistor, representing intrinsic loss within the cell, is instrumental in modelling the performance of the PEMWE stack. This approach allows for a simplified yet effective representation of the dynamic interplay between voltage and current in the electrolysis process, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the system's behaviour.

Figure 3: Static electrical equivalent circuit for PEMWE cell/stack implemented. U_{int} includes all the overvoltages and overpotentials including activation, ohmic and concentration potential.

The voltage of the electrolyser cell is computed as,

$$U_{cell} = U_{rev} + E_{act} + E_{con} + I_{cell}R_{ohm}$$

2)

⁶ Khalid R et al. (2023). Electrical circuit modeling of proton exchange membrane electrolyzer: The state-of-the-art, current challenges, and recommendations. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.

⁷ Atlam, O et al. (2011). Equivalent electrical model for a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyser. Energy Convers. Manag.

where the variation of cell resistance with respect to pressure and temperature takes the form as shown in Equation (1)

The static equivalent circuit models, although effective in computing the static value of voltage, cannot predict the voltage variation during transient operation, and thus effective dynamic models are necessary to simulate a cell's voltage during non-steady-state conditions⁸.

3.1.2. Reversible voltage

It is the electromotive force required to initiate the water electrolysis reaction or gas production. The Nernst equation quantifies the variation of U_{rev} with respect to temperature and pressure⁹.

$$U_{rev} = U_{rev}^0 + \frac{RT_{el}}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{p_{H_2}}{p_0} \left(\frac{p_{O_2}}{p_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad 3)$$

where T_{el} is the electrolyser stack temperature [K], R is the universal gas constant [8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹] and F is Faraday's constant [96485 C mol⁻¹]. U_{rev}^0 is the reversible potential at standard conditions. The partial pressures of hydrogen and oxygen are denoted with p_{H_2} and p_{O_2} respectively.

The hydrogen/oxygen partial pressure is calculated as a difference between the cathode/anode pressure and the saturated water vapour pressure. The cathode and anode pressure are assumed to be 30 bar in this system.

$$\begin{aligned} p_{H_2} &= p_c - p_{H_2O}^{sat} \\ p_{O_2} &= p_a - p_{H_2O}^{sat} \end{aligned} \quad 4)$$

The saturated vapour pressure [bar] with less than 1% error over the range 298 K to 523 K is calculated using equation by Buck¹⁰

$$p_{H_2O}^{sat}(T_{el}) = 0.0061121 \exp \left(\left(18.678 - \frac{T_{el}}{234.5} \right) \left(\frac{T_{el}}{257.14 + T_{el}} \right) \right) \quad 5)$$

Where T_{el} is in degrees Celsius.

⁸ Majumdar, A et al. (2023). Control and control-oriented modeling of PEM water electrolyzers: A review. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.

⁹ Olivier, P et al. (2017). Low-temperature electrolysis system modelling: A review. Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.

¹⁰ Buck, A. L., (1981). New Equations for Computing Vapor Pressure and Enhancement Factor. J. Appl. Meteor. Climatol.

The standard reversible potential, E_{rev}^0 , is computed from the change in Gibbs free energy, ΔG , which is the energy needed to split water into gaseous oxygen and hydrogen.

$$U_{rev}^0 = \frac{\Delta G}{2F}$$

6)

In this work, an empirical expression that relies on temperature is used. In increasing order of complexity, the following temperature-based correlations are used to describe the standard reversible potential¹¹.

$$U_{rev}^0 = 1.5184 - (1.5421 \cdot 10^{-3} T_{stack}) + (9.523 \cdot 10^{-5} T_{stack} \ln T_{stack}) + (9.84 \cdot 10^{-8} T_{stack}^2)$$

7)

3.1.3. Ohmic overvoltage

The ohmic overpotential models the irreversibility which arises from the finite conductivity of the cell. Ohm's law defines the relationship of the current and voltage of the electrolyser with the equivalent resistance.

$$U_{ohm} = j_{el} R_{eq}$$

8)

Where j_{el} is the PEMWE operating current density [$A \text{ cm}^{-2}$]. The value of R_{eq} can include the electric resistance of different elements in the cell, the most important ones are resistance in the electrodes, R_{ele} [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$] and the resistance of the membrane, R_{mem} [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$]¹².

$$R_{eq} = R_{ele} + R_{mem}$$

9)

R_{ele} value assumed from literature¹³. This loss specifically characterises the resistance encountered by protons as they traverse the membrane, and its magnitude is contingent upon various factors including pressure, temperature, and water content within the membrane.

$$R_{mem} = \frac{\delta_{mem}}{\sigma_{mem}}$$

10)

¹¹ Roy, A et al. (2006). Comparison of electrical energy efficiency of atmospheric and high-pressure electrolysers. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy

¹² Marangio, F et al. (2009). Theoretical model and experimental analysis of a high pressure PEM water electrolyser for hydrogen production. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy

¹³ Crespi, E. et al. (2023). Experimental and theoretical evaluation of a 60 kW PEM electrolysis system for flexible dynamic operation. Energy Conversion and Management

where δ_{mem} is the thickness of the membrane, cm and σ_{mem} represent the conductivity of the membrane^{14,15}, [$S\ cm^{-1}$] described by

$$\sigma_{mem} = (0.46\lambda_{mem} - 0.25)\exp\left[-1190\left(\frac{1}{T_{el}} - \frac{1}{298.15}\right)\right] \quad 11)$$

where λ_{mem} is described as moles of water molecules for each mole of a sulfonic acid group in the NafionTM membrane. It is a dimensionless number.

3.1.4. Activation overpotential

It represents the potential loss in overcoming activation barriers to the transfer of species, such as protons, and electrons from electrolyte to electrode. It directly represents the speed of the reactions and is composed of $E_{act,a}$, the activation overpotential for the anode, and $E_{act,c}$, the activation overpotential for the cathode, such that

$$E_{act} = E_{act,a} + E_{act,c} \quad 12)$$

Various expressions are proposed in the literature to determine the activation overpotential required for both the anode and cathode. In the present work, the Butler-Volmer equation is inverted exactly assuming that the charge transfer coefficient α is equal to 0.5:

$$E_{act,i} = \frac{RT}{F} \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{j}{2j_{i0}}\right) \quad i \in \{a, c\} \quad 13)$$

j is the current density [$A\ cm^{-2}$], and j_{a0} and j_{c0} are the respective exchange current densities of the anode and cathode [$A\ cm^{-2}$].

3.1.5. Concentration overpotential

The concentration overpotential, also denoted as the diffusion overpotential, models the resistance due to the mass transport limitations of reactants in the electrode. At high current densities, the oxygen bubbles at the anode block the electrode at low current densities, the ohmic and activation overpotentials are significantly larger than the concentration overpotential, thus the concentration overpotential is often neglected in these operating conditions. Concentration overpotential can be described as the sum of the concentration overpotentials in the anode and cathode, $E_{con,a}$ and $E_{con,c}$, respectively^{16,17}.

¹⁴ Meier, F et al. (2004). Transport parameters for the modelling of water transport in ionomer membranes for PEM-fuel cells. *Electrochim. Acta*.
¹⁵ Dickinson, E. J. F et al. (2020). Modelling the Proton-Conductive Membrane in Practical Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) Simulation: A Review. *Membranes*.
¹⁶ Weber, A et al. (2010). Mass transfer at two-phase and three-phase interfaces. In *Handbook of Fuel Cells : Fundamentals, Technology and Applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
¹⁷ García-Valverde, R et al. (2012). Simple PEM water electrolyser model and experimental validation. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*.

$$E_{diff} = E_{con} = E_{con,a} + E_{con,c}$$

14)

$$E_{con,i} = \frac{RT}{2k_iF} \ln \left(1 + \frac{j}{j_{l,i}} \right) \quad i \in \{a, c\}$$

15)

where k_i is an empirically derived coefficient and j_l is the limiting current density based on the diffusion capabilities [$A \text{ cm}^{-2}$]. These values are typically determined from curve fitting of experimental data.

Figure 4 PEMWE cell electrochemical potential [V] as a function of current density [$A \text{ cm}^{-2}$] with contributions from various overpotentials such as activation, ohmic and concentration (diffusion). The activation overpotential dominated at current densities below $0.5 A \text{ cm}^{-2}$, ohmic above $0.5 A \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

3.2. Thermal models

Temperature significantly influences the operational dynamics of a PEMWE cell. The inclusion of thermal sub-models aids in monitoring temperature fluctuations during cell operation. The significance of temperature extends beyond the endothermic nature of the electrolysis reaction, including cell ageing, degradation processes, system efficiency, and safety considerations. However, the irreversible processes within a water electrolyser cell are exothermic. In this work, the thermal management system is developed based on a demonstration project¹⁸. A steady state thermal balance is given as:

¹⁸ Espinosa-López, M., et al. (2018). Modelling and experimental validation of a 46 kW PEM high-pressure water electrolyzer. Renewable Energy

$$Q_{net} = Q_{gen} - Q_{cool} - Q_{loss} - Q_{misc}$$

16)

The net heat generation Q_{net} [W] is composed of varied heat sources and sinks in the system. The terms described in the net heat generation of the system include Q_{gen} , which describes heat generation, Q_{loss} , heat lost to the surrounding environment, Q_{cool} , which describes heat transferred to the coolant, and Q_{misc} , representing other miscellaneous phenomena such as heat transferred from the pump. Thermal models used for PEMWE modelling are often expressed in the form of ordinary differential equations (ODE), neglecting spatial temperature variations, or more intricate partial differential equations (PDE) that account for such variations. Equation 18, derived from the first law of thermodynamics, shows an energy balance for an open system, coupled with a lumped thermal capacitance model, is employed to characterise temperature dynamics¹⁹. Assuming the output species temperatures are equal to stack temperature and the input species temperatures are equal both at anode and cathode compartments, enthalpy of species balance at steady state are same as standard enthalpy of reaction.

$$C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = \sum h_i n_{i_{in}} - \sum h_i n_{i_{out}} + \dot{Q}_{loss}$$

$$\approx \underbrace{IN_{cell} \left(U_{cell} - \frac{\Delta H_r}{2zF} \right)}_{\text{heat generated}} + \underbrace{\sum m_w c_{p,w} (T_{in} - T_{out})}_{\text{heat transferred to coolant}} + \underbrace{\dot{Q}_{loss}}_{\text{heat lost to environment}}$$

17)

C_p is the lumped thermal capacitance of the stack, ΔH_r molar enthalpy of reaction, \dot{Q}_{loss} thermal exchanges between the stack and its environment. The transient heat generation from the electrolysis process can be expressed as

$$\dot{Q}_{gen} = N_c (E_{cell} - E_{tn}) \times I$$

18)

where I is the PEMWE current [A], which is calculated as product of the current density, j_{el} , and the active area of the cell, A_{cell} [cm²]. N_c is the number of cells in the stack, allows the total heat generation of the electrolyser to be calculated. The thermoneutral voltage, E_{tn} [V], describes the heat energy contained in the chemical reaction.

$$E_{tn} = -\frac{\Delta H}{2F}$$

19)

¹⁹ Vielstich, W et al. (2010). Handbook of Fuel Cells : Fundamentals, Technology and Applications. John Wiley & Sons.

where ΔH , the change in enthalpy from the electrolysis reaction is expressed by $\Delta H = \Delta G + T\Delta S$. ΔG and ΔS describe the change in Gibbs free energy and entropy for the reaction, respectively.

The cooling rate represents the amount of energy that the thermal management system of the electrolyser must remove from the system to avoid overheating the electrolyser. In most cases, this is achieved by flowing excess water through the anode side of the cell to help keep it cool. This water is in excess of the water consumed due to the electrolysis reaction, water loss from vents/drains and water loss due to impurities (water with increased conductivity from the substances leaching out from the electrolyser needs to be removed/cleaned). In this study, the water losses and water consumption in the PEM electrolyser are two orders of magnitude lower than what is needed for cooling. Therefore, to calculate the amount of heat loss to the excess water, it is assumed that only the water required for cooling the stack needs to be accounted for in \dot{m}_{H_2O} of Equation 21. The simplified energy balance for a closed system²⁰ is therefore,

$$\dot{Q}_{water\ cooling} = \dot{m}_{H_2O} c_{p,H_2O} (T_{H_2O}^{in} - T_{H_2O}^{out}) \quad 20)$$

where \dot{m}_{H_2O} and c_{p,H_2O} are the mass flow rate [$kg\ s^{-1}$], and specific heat of the PEMWE exhaust water [$JK^{-1}kg^{-1}$] respectively, $T_{H_2O}^{in}$, $T_{H_2O}^{out}$ [K] are water temperatures in, and out of the PEMWE. To control the temperature of the electrolyser, the mass flow rate depends on the amount of heat to be removed assuming the inlet and outlet temperatures are to be maintained.

In addition to the heat management in the stack, the water flowing from the oxygen-side gas liquid separator heading towards the electrolyser loses heat to a coolant in the heat exchanger as shown in Figure 3. In the model, this is done by cooling the water flowing from the stack anode outlet back into the stack inlet, since a gas liquid separator is not yet modelled. Figure 5 shows how the water from the PEMWE outlet is pumped, then cooled through the heat exchanger on its way back to the stack. The value of cooling can also be approximated using the following equation.

$$\dot{Q}_{coolant} = h A LMTD \quad 21)$$

where h and A are the heat transfer coefficient, and heat transfer area respectively, LMTD is logarithmic mean temperature difference. It is the ratio of temperature difference between the two streams at inlet and outlet.

²⁰ Lebbal, M. E. et al. (2009). Identification and monitoring of a PEM electrolyser based on dynamical modelling. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy

Figure 5 In the thermal management system, coolant flowrate (\dot{m}_{co} , [kg s⁻¹]) is controlled to maintain temperature using pumps, a heat exchanger, a PID controller and tanks.

The temperature of water out from the heat exchanger is maintained at 330.15 K by changing the flow rate of the coolant. The coolant used is an ethylene-water (40:60 by mass) mixture. Q_{loss} and Q_{misc} are neglected.

3.3. Mass balance and transport models

Mass transport sub models describe the movement of chemical species within the cell and are employed to calculate concentrations and membrane properties, such as gas crossover and water uptake. In this work we do not include the gas crossover but introduce its effect on faradaic efficiency. A comprehensive review of mass transport and fluid modelling is performed by Maier et al.²¹, however, this section focuses on a mass balance and transport model that can be used in control design and analysis.

²¹ Maier, M et.al. (2022). Mass transport in PEM water electrolyzers: A review. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy

Figure 6 VirtualELY model showing the internal electrical model (described in Section 3.1) and thermo-fluidic circuit (described in Section 3.2) of PEMWE stack. The deionised (DI) water is introduced from H2OToStack port (1), where the electric current from the electrical circuit is utilised to produce hydrogen (3) and oxygen (2) gas. The heat generated in PEMWE stack is transferred to the feed DI water through thermal capacitance $HC_{stack} [JK^{-1}]$ and thermal conductor $TC_{stack} [Wm^{-1}K^{-1}]$

The electrolysis reaction produces hydrogen and oxygen by splitting water. An ODE model for mass transport begins with quantifying reactions in Section 2. The molar production rate of hydrogen (\dot{n}_{H_2}) within the cathode half-reaction (in section 2) of the electrolyser is,

$$\dot{n}_{H_2} = \frac{j_{el} N_{cell}}{2F} \eta_F \quad (22)$$

Where the current density is j_{el} , and the number of cells in the electrolyser stack is N_{cell} , the Faradaic efficiency is η_F . Using the reaction stoichiometry, the oxygen production, \dot{n}_{O_2} , and water production, \dot{n}_{H_2O} , in the anode are estimated using,

$$\dot{n}_{O_2} = \frac{j_{el} N_{cell}}{4F} \eta_F \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{n}_{H_2O} = -\frac{j_{el} N_{cell}}{2F} \eta_F \quad (24)$$

The Faraday efficiency, η_F , accounts for all the electrons that are not involved in the electrolysis reaction; however, in some cases it is assumed to be greater than 99%²².

The flow of these species within the electrolyser are modelled in separate domains of the anode, cathode, and membrane.

3.3.1. Anode

Within the anode, water is split and oxygen forms. The instantaneous change in molar concentration of oxygen and water is computed using the conservation of mass.

$$\frac{dn_{O_2}}{dt} = \dot{n}_{O_2}^{in} - \dot{n}_{O_2}^{out} + \dot{n}_{O_2}^p \quad 25)$$

$$\frac{dn_{H_2O}}{dt} = \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{in} - \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{out} - \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{mem} + \dot{n}_{H_2O}^p \quad 26)$$

where \dot{n}_{O_2/H_2O}^{in} , \dot{n}_{O_2/H_2O}^{out} and \dot{n}_{O_2/H_2O}^p [mol s⁻¹] are the inlet, outlet and production molar flow rates of oxygen and water at the anode, respectively. $\dot{n}_{H_2O}^{mem}$ is the flow rate of water across the membrane. $\frac{dn_{O_2/H_2O}}{dt}$ is the rate of change in the species concentration at anode.

3.3.2. Cathode

On the cathode side, hydrogen is formed and there is water crossover across the membrane, such that the balance of these species is given as

$$\frac{dn_{H_2}}{dt} = \dot{n}_{H_2}^{in} - \dot{n}_{H_2}^{out} + \dot{n}_{H_2}^p \quad 27)$$

$$\frac{dn_{H_2O}}{dt} = \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{in} - \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{out} + \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{mem} \quad 28)$$

where \dot{n}_{H_2/H_2O}^{in} , \dot{n}_{H_2/H_2O}^{out} and \dot{n}_{H_2/H_2O}^p [mol s⁻¹] are the inlet and outlet molar flow rates of hydrogen and water at cathode, respectively.

3.3.3. Membrane

In the membrane, water is transported by electro-osmotic drag, back-diffusion, and convection generated by pressure gradient. The molar flux of water through the cathode describes the movement of water across the membrane originating from the anode.

²² Yodwong, B. et al. (2020). Faraday's Efficiency Modeling of a Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolyzer Based on Experimental Data. Energies

Conversely, the molar flux of water through the anode represents water consumption through the reaction and its crossover to the cathode.

The total water that crosses the membrane is described in literature as the sum of three components²³ as follows,

$$\dot{n}_{H_2O}^{mem} = \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{diff} + \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{eod} - \dot{n}_{H_2O}^{hyd} \quad (29)$$

where $\dot{n}_{H_2O}^{diff}$ and $\dot{n}_{H_2O}^{eod}$ [mol s⁻¹] are the molar flow rates of water due to diffusion and electro-osmotic drag from anode to cathode and $\dot{n}_{H_2O}^{hyd}$ [mol s⁻¹] is the flow rate from the hydraulic pressure effects from cathode to anode. These three terms describe the driving forces behind the flow of water across the membrane.

Diffusion of water across the membrane (relevant only for electrolyzers where one electrode is not fully humidified), is calculated from Fick's law of diffusion. Assuming a linear water concentration gradient, we can simply calculate the concentration gradients across the membrane²⁴ as,

$$\dot{n}_{H_2O}^{diff} = AD_w \frac{dc_w}{dy} = \frac{A}{\delta_{mem}} \int_{c_w^a}^{c_w^c} D_w dy = \frac{AD_w}{\delta_{mem}} (C_w^c - C_w^a) \quad (30)$$

where A is the active area, D_w is the diffusion coefficient of water in the membrane [cm² s⁻¹], and δ_{mem} is the membrane thickness [cm]. $C_{H_2O}^{c/a}$ water concentration at the electrolyte/electrode interfaces. The water concentration in liquid form at anode and cathode²⁵ can be expressed as

$$C_w^{c/a} = \frac{\rho_{w,T^{c/a}}}{mw_w} \quad (31)$$

mw_w is the molecular weight of water [kg mol⁻¹], and $\rho_{H_2O,T^{c/a}} = A/B^{1+(1-T/C)^D}$ [kg m⁻³] A, B, C and D are empirical parameters.

The water diffusion coefficient is essentially a modified Arrhenius equation based on experimental measurements and it is shown that it strongly depends on the water content and temperature²⁶.

²³ Grigoriev, S. A et al. (2010). Mathematical modeling of high-pressure PEM water electrolysis. Journal of Applied Electrochemistry.

²⁴ Liso, V., et al. (2018). Modelling and Experimental Analysis of a Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Water Electrolysis Cell at Different Operating Temperatures. Energies

²⁵ Gu, W et al. (2010). Proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) down-the-channel performance model . Handbook of Fuel Cells.

²⁶ Caulk, D. A., et.al. (2012). A Steady Permeation Method for Measuring Water Transport Properties of Fuel Cell Membranes. J. Electrochem. Soc.

$$D_w = 0.05\lambda(1 + 247 \exp(-0.66\lambda)) \cdot 10^{-6}$$

32)

D_w is originally correlated based on experimental measurements between 30 and 80°C using the ionomer (polymer electrolyte). The diffusion coefficient, D is sensitively dependent on the membrane hydration. For PEMWE we consider Nafion™ 1110 highly hydrated i.e λ_{mem} is greater than 4.5²⁷.

The water diffusivity in membrane is a strong function of membrane water content, λ ^{21, 28}

$$\lambda = \left[1 + 0.2325 RH^2 \left(\frac{T - 30}{30} \right) \times [14.22RH^3 - 18.92RH^2 + 13.41RH] \right]$$

33)

Where RH is the relative humidity (in fraction) that the membrane is exposed to.

$$RH = \frac{p_w}{p_w^{sat}(T_{el})}$$

34)

The water transport resulting from electro-osmotic drag, denoted as \dot{n}_{mem}^{eod} , quantifies the number of moles of water molecules that are entrained by each mole of hydrogen ions during their passage through the membrane. This phenomenon is directly proportional to the osmotic drag coefficient and the concentration of hydrogen ions.

$$\dot{n}_{mem}^{eod} = \frac{n_d I}{F}$$

35)

The electro-osmotic drag coefficient, denoted as n_d , quantifies the number of water molecules transported per hydrogen ion, and its determination relies on experimental measurements. However, it is noteworthy that values reported in the literature exhibit considerable variance across different studies conducted by various authors²⁹.

The relationship between the electro-osmotic drag coefficient and water content in the membrane is given by following equation that is developed by curve fitting the values of water content in the membrane and electro-osmotic drag coefficient^{30,31},

²⁷ Kusoglu, A et al (2017). New Insights into Perfluorinated Sulfonic-Acid Ionomers. Chemical Reviews.

²⁸ Gu, W et al. (2010). Proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) down-the-channel performance model. Handbook of Fuel Cells.

²⁹ Dickinson, E. J. F., et al. (2020). Modelling the Proton-Conductive Membrane in Practical Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) Simulation: A Review. Membranes.

³⁰ Dutta, S., Shimpalee, S., & Van Zee, J. W. (2001). Numerical prediction of mass-exchange between cathode and anode channels in a PEM fuel cell. Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.

³¹ Springer, T. E., Zawodzinski, T. A., & Gottesfeld, S. (1993). Polymer Electrolyte Fuel Cell Model. J. Electrochem. Soc.

$$n_d = 0.0029\lambda^2 + 0.05\lambda - 3.9 \times 10^{-19}$$

36)

The rate of water transport from the cathode to the anode across the membrane depends on the pressure gradient and the water transport resulting from such gradient is described by Darcy's Law.

$$\dot{n}_{mem}^p = \frac{K_{Darcy} A_{cell} \rho_w \Delta P}{\delta_{mem} \mu_w M_w}$$

37)

where K_{Darcy} is the membrane permeability is assumed $1.58 \times 10^{-18} \text{ [m}^2\text{]}$ and is the dynamic viscosity of water $[\text{g cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}]$.

3.4. Electrolyser efficiency

In comprehending the functionality of a PEMWE from a system engineering standpoint, the paramount parameter is efficiency. The total energy efficiency of the cell, denoted as η_{el} , is characterised by the product of several discrete efficiencies.

$$\eta_{el} = \eta_v \eta_F$$

38)

η_v stands for the voltage efficiency, η_F represents the faradaic efficiency. Specifically, the voltage efficiency (η_v) is elucidated by the disparity between the ideal reversible voltage (U_{rev}) and the actual cell voltage (U_{cell}), as determined by the electrochemical model.

$$\eta_v = \frac{V_{rev}}{V_{cell}}$$

39)

The faradaic efficiency η_F is subject to change upon the presence of hydrogen and oxygen crossover across the membrane, typically converging towards unity. Nevertheless, at low current densities, its significance becomes more pronounced. Gas crossover primarily results from a solution-diffusion mechanism³².

$$\eta_F = \frac{j_{useful}}{j_{el}} = 1 - \left(\frac{j_{H2,x} - j_{O2,x}}{j_{el}} \right)$$

40)

The equivalent current associated with hydrogen and oxygen crossover³³ $[\text{A cm}^{-2}]$,

³² Onda, K et al. (2002). Performance Analysis of Polymer-Electrolyte Water Electrolysis Cell at a Small-Unit Test Cell and Performance Prediction of Large Stacked Cell. J. Electrochem. Soc.

³³ Kocha, S.S., et al. (2006), Characterization of gas crossover and its implications in PEM fuel cells†. AIChE J.

$$j_{i,x} = \frac{2Fk_i}{\delta_{mem}} p_{i,c} \quad i \in \{a, c\}$$

41)

The hydrogen permeability [mol bar⁻¹ cm⁻¹ s⁻¹] in Nafion™³⁴ is

$$k_{H_2} = 6.6 \cdot 10^{-13} \exp\left(-\frac{E_A}{RT}\right)$$

42)

E_A is 21030 [J mol⁻¹]. The oxygen permeability is approximated to be half of hydrogen permeability.

3.4.1. Gross specific energy consumption

The specific electrical energy consumption of the electrolyser system, ϵ , describes the net amount of electrical power, P_{el} , in kW consumed by the PEMWE per kg of H₂ produced per hour.

$$\epsilon = \frac{P_{el}}{\dot{m}_{H_2} \cdot 3600}$$

43)

The system's net specific energy consumption comprises of four sources of energy consumption; the electrolysis process or stack energy consumption (that is voltage efficiency), the energy losses associated with physical loss of H₂ (faradaic efficiency), energy consumption associated with the AC/DC power electronics, and the ancillary balance of plant energy consumption. The energy consumption due to AC/DC power electronics, and the ancillary balance of plant energy consumption are significant only at low load conditions. This excludes BoP consumption.

4. Simulation results

The simulation results consist of two parts, 1. Analysis of the dynamics of the input power fed to the PEMWE system from a wind park, 2. Estimated KPIs of the PEMWE system.

The input wind power from the wind park is normalised (0- no power and 1- full power) and is found to be varying significantly. To find out the degree of variation and frequency, distribution plots were made as shown in Figure 7 b and c. At an hourly scale, it is found that the input power from wind ramps up and down by a maximum of 50% but variation between approximately ±20% occurred significantly. Finally, it is found that the wind park either was not operational or was curtailed for approximately 17% of the time, 64% of the time it varied between no load and full load, and 18% of the time was at full load capacity.

a

³⁴ Liso, V., et al. (2018). Modelling and Experimental Analysis of a Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Water Electrolysis Cell at Different Operating Temperatures. Energies

Figure 7 (a) Input power profile from a wind park for a year at an hourly resolution. (b) Rate of power change from wind park as a function of time (c) Histogram of wind power for a year

Figure 8 Performance indicators of PEMWE system.

The Figure 8 shows estimates on hydrogen production, DI water consumption, specific electrical energy and stack temperature. The input power from the wind park fed to the

PEMWE system produces hydrogen and consumes DI water proportionally. These estimates are normalised to their rated capacity to demonstrate the dynamics. The specific energy consumption is proportional to input power or hydrogen production and varies between 45 to 61.3 kWh kg⁻¹H₂. The stack temperature was maintained at setpoint 330.15 K with a variation of maximum ± 0.017 K h⁻¹ from the setpoint.

